

CTD Processing Report for the July 2016 ASCA/SEAmester Survey

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1. Introduction

This data has been processed and corrected before. Final errors after salinity regression correction on the quality-controlled, processed July 2016 ASCA/SEAmester CTD data were approximately 0.006 PSU, 3 times the international requirement of 0.002 PSU. Additionally, there were several queries with regards to the impact of the salinity calibration applied to the data. Figure 1 indicates that the salinity values of the 2016 data were lower than data collected from other surveys of the same region. For these reasons, we attempt to re-apply the corrections on the conductivity data using primarily the method described in the “Extended report on CTD processing for ASCA0618” by Shane Elipot.

Figure 1: T-S diagram from the June 2016 ASCA CTD survey (each CTD cast is shown in a different colour). The July 2016 ASCA/ SEAmester survey data is shown in black. Historical AUCE and ACT CTD data is shown in grey. The figure on the right is a close up of the deep water masses (Elipot, 2018).

2. Data

The raw salinity data were re-processed according to the best practice methods by James Maitland, the method used is consistent across all the SEAmester cruises of the ASCA transect. This report outlines the methodology used to apply corrections to the quality-controlled, processed CTD conductivity data using the salinity bottle (Portasal) data.

The CTD bottle files, which contain quality-controlled, processed data from the depths at which the Niskin bottles were closed, were compared to the Portasal data. The CTD used for the survey had 2 sensors for measuring conductivity and 2 for measuring temperature, and one pressure sensor (amongst other sensors). CTD conductivity sensor 1 (2) was paired with temperature sensor 1 (2) to determine salinity value 1 (2). Hereafter, all of the values from CTD sensor set 1 and 2 are referred to as CTD1 and CTD2, respectively. Figure 2 reveals that although the two CTD salinity values compare well, there is a negative bias in the CTD data when compared to the Portasal values.

Figure 2: Salinity differences between the Portasal and CTD. Portasal – Portasal values are indicated in black, Portasal- CTD1 in blue and Portasal CTD2 are indicated in red.

The consistency in the Standard Sea Water Sample readings recorded at the beginning and the end of running the samples implies that there was no drift in the Portasal.

We use 165 bottle samples, where the 3 consecutive salinity readings taken for each sample did not differ by more than 0.002 PSU (the internationally required accuracy). Conductivity was calculated from salinity values using `gsw_C_from_SP` from the TEOS-10 MATLAB toolbox. Two sets of values are computed, one using temperature values from CTD1 and the other using temperature values from CTD2. The pressure values used are common to the 2 sets. For each sample, the median value of the three calculated conductivity values was taken as the final sample value.

3. Comparisons of Portasal and CTD conductivity values.

For 12 of the 165 calculated conductivity values, the difference in conductivity between the two sets of values is greater than 0.003 mS/cm, the expected accuracy of the CTD sensors. These sample values are therefore discarded from the regression analyses used to correct the CTD conductivity.

It is well known that conductivity is a function of salinity, temperature and pressure. Figure 3 compares Portasal and CTD conductivity values as a function of conductivity, pressure, time and temperature. Linear regressions in each case indicate that the differences of conductivity value are a significant function of conductivity, time and temperature but not of pressure (Table 1). The negative bias of the CTD data is also evident in Figure 3.

Table 1: The slope and y-intercept of the data represented in Figure 3 ($y = mx + c$)

Conductivity differences as a function of:	CTD 1 slope; intercept	CTD2 slope; intercept
Conductivity	-8.2048e-04; 0.0135	-8.4334e-04; 0.0150
Pressure	3.0244e-06; -0.0228	3.0885e-06; -0.0222
Time	0.0039; -0.0589	0.0040; -0.0591
Temperature	-7.6665e-04; -0.0108	-7.8766e-04; -0.0100

Figure 3: Conductivity differences between CTD and Portasal values and as a function of a) Conductivity, b) Pressure, c) Time and d) Temperature.

4. Regression

We derive coefficients for the following correction models:

Model A: $C_C = \alpha C + \gamma$

Model AA: $C_C = \alpha C$

Model B: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta P + \gamma$

Model BB: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta P$

Model C: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta T + \gamma$

Model CC: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta T$

Model D: $C_c = \alpha C + \beta t + \gamma$

Model DD: $C_c = \alpha C + \beta t$

Where C represents conductivity, P represents pressure, T represents temperature and t represents time. α , β and γ are derived for both CTD1 and CTD2 using the least squares method, regressing the CTD data against the sample calculated conductivity. For models AA, BB, CC and DD γ is equal to 0.

For all models, the adjusted R^2 value was very close to 1. However for both sets of sensors, Model DD reveals adjusted R^2 values that are slightly closer to 1 than the other models (Table 2, which shows 1- the adjusted R^2 value). For this reason we chose model DD as the best model for July 2016 ASCA/SEAmester CTD data.

Table 2: Adjusted R^2 values from the different models for CTD1 and CTD2

CTD1		CTD2	
Model	[1- Adjusted R^2]	Model	[1- Adjusted R^2]
A1	0.5633e-05	A2	0.5654e-05
AA1	0.5705e-05	AA2	0.5752e-05
B1	0.5671e-05	B2	0.5692e-05
BB1	0.5667e-05	BB2	0.5698e-05
C1	0.5668e-05	C2	0.5689e-05
CC1	0.5631e-05	CC2	0.5652e-05
D1	0.5616e-05	D2	0.5635e-05
DD1	0.5588e-05	DD2	0.5614e-05

Figures 4, 5, 6 and 7 below show a graphical representation of the results for the correction models BB (model BB was found to be the most accurate for the June 2016 ASCA survey and we wanted to observe the differences between the different models) and DD.

Figure 4: Results of regression for conductivity for model BB after removing large residuals.

Figure 5: Results of regression for salinity for model BB after removing large residuals.

Figure 6: Results of regression for conductivity for model DD after removing large residuals.

Figure 7: Results of regression for salinity for model DD after removing large residuals.

Table 3: Results from second regression for conductivity and salinity for model BB.

	Sensor Set 1	Sensor Set 2
α	1.0005	1.0005
β	-3.6293e-07	-4.8207e-07
$\hat{\sigma}$ Conductivity (mS/cm)	0.0047	0.0048
$\hat{\sigma}$ Salinity (PSU)	0.0047	0.0048
$\hat{\sigma}$ Salinity (PSU) for P>2000 dbar	0.0046	0.0047
$\hat{\sigma}$ Salinity (PSU) for P<2000 dbar	0.0047	0.0049

Table 4: Results from second regression for conductivity and salinity for model DD.

	Sensor Set 1	Sensor Set 2
α	1.0005	1.0005
β	-4.6300e-04	-6.3231e-04
$\hat{\sigma}$ Conductivity (mS/cm)	0.0055	0.0056
$\hat{\sigma}$ Salinity (PSU)	0.0053	0.0054

$\hat{\sigma}$ is the square root of the mean square error (an estimate of the final error or uncertainty for conductivity). Using both model BB and DD, this error is more than 3×10^{-3} mS/cm for both sensors (this is higher than the acceptable standard).

We further estimate $\hat{\sigma}$ for salinity. For both model BB and model DD the error is ~ 2.5 times the required accuracy of 0.002 for international standards. This value is however slightly smaller than the error of the previous salinity regression correction of 0.006 PSU.

5. Finalising the data

We find the error in CTD sensor 1 to be slightly smaller than the error from CTD sensor 2, and therefore choose to correct the data according to sensor 1. We correct the data according to both model BB and model DD for comparison purposes and compare it to historical ACT data (Figure 8). The data from model BB is barely visible in Figure 8, as it lies almost directly beneath the data from model DD, showing that the correction from the different models yields very similar results in this case. Upon further investigation we observe that at depth, the salinometer salinity values are higher than previously observed salinities across the ACT/ASCA transect. For the deeper water masses, the salinity is not expected to vary from the historical values. In addition to the salinity values being too high, the range in the salinity from the salinometer is also too broad (pink dots, Figure 8). It's possible that the Portasal was giving slightly inaccurate readings, impacting the final dataset. For these reasons we opt to use the uncorrected CTD data as the final salinity data for the July 2016 ASCA/SEAmester survey.

Figure 8: T-S diagram comparing the data from the ACT cruises to the July 2016 ASCA/ SEAmester data. The ACT data is shown in dark blue orange and yellow. Purple dots correspond to uncorrected July 2016 SEAmester salinity values, green and light blue dots show the July 2016 SEAmester salinity values corrected according to model BB and DD, respectively (green is barely visible). The larger pink dots show the salinometer salinity values. The figure on the right is a zoom of the deeper water masses in the left hand figure.

In Figure 8 we observe a small unexpected spike in the data near the grey 27.8 kg.m^{-3} density contour. Closer examination reveals that this spike is predominantly from 1 CTD cast (purple line, Figure 9), and we have removed the spike from that cast. The salinities of the remaining 19 casts remain unchanged in the final dataset for the July 2016 ASCA/ SEAmester CTD survey.

Figure 9: T-S diagram of the deeper water masses showing each CTD cast in a different colour.